

No injuries from cold temperatures were observed in traditional varieties Chhomro and Raksali at the seedling stage; most improved lines had either discolored leaves or stunted yellowish growth. Chhomro and Raksali consistently performed better than the exotic cold-tolerant materials for 2 yr. Spikelet sterility on exotic lines was

large (25–100%); no sterility was noticed in Chhomro (Table 1). Yields of Chhomro were significantly superior to those of Raksali in 1986 (Table 2). Widely grown Raksali suffered some spikelet sterility and yielded relatively less than Chhomro.

Most of the exotic lines from

NCTR and IRCTN failed to set grain at Lumle. Chhomro yields ranged from 4.8 to 5.3 t/ha under rainfed wetland conditions.

Chhomro's cold tolerance could be utilized in developing suitable cold-tolerant rice varieties for temperate areas of Nepal and elsewhere. □

Low temperature tolerance of traditional Vietnamese varieties

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About 2.5 million ha of rice in Vietnam is subjected to low temperature. In the north, low temperature killed 27,110 ha of rice seedlings in 1976.

The first crop Nov–Jun is subjected to low temperatures Nov–Mar (5.0 to 11.0°C minimum temperature), coupled with low sunshine hours (1.3–4.5 h/d). The most common cold injury symptoms are seedling stunting, leaf wilting or even death, spikelet degeneration, poor grain filling, high sterility, and delayed growth.

We evaluated the cold tolerance of 475 traditional Vietnamese rice varieties from the International Rice Germplasm Center to identify possible donor parents for breeding.

The entries could be grouped into five categories: 1) glutinous (mostly japonica), 2) mountain area, 3) winter rice, 4) wet season rice in the north, and 5) wet season rice in the south (Table 1).

Table 1. Response of Vietnamese rice groups to low temperature at the seedling stage. Hanoi, Vietnam.

Group	Varieties (no.) with cold tolerance at seedling stage		
	Good	Poor	Total
Glutinous	9	28	37
Mountain area	4	30	34
Winter rice (Chiem)	14	77	91
Wet season (north)	0	92	92
Wet season (south)	12	209	221
Total	39	436	475

The mountain and winter varieties include many japonicas. Both north and south wet season varieties are indica types.

Varieties were tested at the seedling stage (10°C for 4 d), panicle initiation (17°C for 15 d), and anthesis (17°C for 10 d). At the seedling stage, 39 entries — many of them winter rice varieties — showed cold hardiness (Table 1). A large number of the varieties used in the mountains did not have cold tolerance at the seedling stage. Some glutinous varieties showed cold tolerance at the seedling stage.

Winter rices usually are divided into six subgroups on the basis of morphological characteristics. The Tep group had the highest number of cold-tolerant varieties (Table 2).

The rice plant is most sensitive to low temperature at meiosis or panicle initiation. The outstanding Vietnam entry tolerant of 17°C air temperature at panicle initiation was Bong Sen (Acc. 10861) with a score of 1; Tep Trang and Ba Ren were relatively tolerant at

Table 2. Winter season Vietnam varieties (Chiem) and their response to low temperature at the seedling stage. Hanoi, Vietnam.

Group	Varieties (no.) with indicated cold tolerance		
	Good	Poor	Total
Te (nonglutinous rice)	3	4	7
Tep (fine, short grain)	4	5	9
Cut (round grain)	0	6	6
Bau (large grain)	2	10	12
Saiduong (brown glume)	3	3	6
Other Chiem varieties	29	23	52

panicle initiation and at the seedling stage.

Most of the varieties had relatively poor tolerance at anthesis. The most tolerant are Bong Sen, Nep Da, Nep Den (Acc. 24149), Bat Goat (Acc. 24193), Ba Ren, Tep 62, and Khau Mua Venh.

Ba Ren and Tep 62 are the most promising. Scores for the other Vietnamese varieties are available from the IRGC data bank. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Potassium nutrition in hybrid rice

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We studied hybrid rice Vu 35 at different K levels on a Quaternary red clay soil with pH 6.0, 2.76% organic matter, 70 ppm available K, 240 ppm

slowly available K, and 0.188% N. Conventional variety Xiang 9 was the check.

KC1 was applied at 0, 110, 220, and 440 kg/ha in main plots with 350 kg urea and 550 kg superphosphate/ha. All the P, 2/3 N, and 1/3 K were applied before transplanting, 1/3 N and 2/3 K at tillering. The 2 varieties were transplanted in 4- × 8-m subplots with 3

Table 1. Effect of K level on growth of hybrid rice Vu 35.^a Hunan, China.

K level (kg KCl/ha)	Tillering	Panicle initiation	Full heading	Maturity
	<i>Leaf area index</i>			
0	1.63	4.51	6.69	2.19
110	1.52	4.80	8.39**	3.64**
220	1.68	4.88	8.44**	4.34**
440	1.71	4.04	9.71**	4.10**
	<i>Net assimilation rate (A Dry matter mg/dm² per h)</i>			
0	10.5	12.3	8.1	7.0
110	1.9	13.3	9.0	9.3
220	8.6	9.5	11.0	8.9
440	10.9	13.2	11.4	8.9
	<i>Dry matter weight (g/plant)</i>			
0	2.73	8.13	19.47	27.17
110	2.73	8.27	26.10*	34.93*
220	2.96	8.30	21.97	33.73*
440	3.23	8.30	28.10*	35.27*

^aSignificance at the 5% (*) or 1% (**) levels by Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 2. Effect of K fertilization on yield and K absorption by hybrid rice and a conventional variety. Hunan, China.

Variety	K level (kg KCl/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	K absorbed (kg/ha)	K depleted (kg/t grain)	Grain increase (kg/kg K ₂ O)
Vu 35	0	8.5	107.8	12.72	
	100	8.7	147.9	16.92	4.8
	220	8.8	198.4	22.54	2.9
	440	9.2	250.9	27.42	3.0
Xiang 9	0	7.3	88.95	12.25	
	110	7.6	144.2	18.88	6.6
	220	7.4	190.3	25.68	1.3
	440	7.6	195.3	25.80	1.6

replications. Samples were taken at transplanting, tillering, panicle initiation, full heading, and maturity for soil, plant, and yield analyses.

Increased K increased K content in plant and absorbed K increased with increased K fertilizer at all stages for both varieties; however, Vu 35 was more sensitive to K supplied from panicle initiation to heading and needed more K. The leaf area index was significantly correlated with plant N content ($r = 0.91^*$) at early growth stages and with plant K content ($r = 0.94$) at late growth stages. Total photosynthetic area and net assimilation rate had increased significantly at heading and maturing stages, which led to 13-44% increase in dry matter production with K application (Table 1).

Grain yield of Vu 35 increased 3-8% with K level, but increase/kg K₂O applied declined (Table 2), resulting in lower K economic efficiency at higher K levels. Yield of Xiang 9 was significantly lower than that of Vu 35 and did not show obvious response to K fertilization. □

Test cross for restorer genes using three male sterile lines

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We tested crosses for restorer genes for the Thailand hybrid rice breeding program in 1982. Now we have 8 varieties and 10 elite breeding lines that are effective restorers for V20A. In 1985, we received male sterile lines IR46828A and IR46829A from IRRI and crossed 5 varieties and 10 elite breeding lines as male parents with 3 CMS lines — V20A, IR46828A, and IR46829A (which are the same WA type) — to identify their restorers (see table).

The F₁ hybrids were grown in the field. Spikelet fertility was evaluated visually for each plant. Varieties showing more than 80% spikelet fertility were classified as restorers. those

Restorers and maintainers^a for CMS lines V20A, IR46828A, and IR46829A in Thailand, 1986.

Variety	V20A	IR46828A	IR46829A
IR11418-19-2-3	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR75007-16-3-1	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR76037-2-164-1-1	M	M	M
CNTBR71011-59-2-2-2	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR76035-PSL-16-1-2	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR80187-21-1-1	PR	PR	PR
BKNLR77011-31-1-1-1-1	PR	PR	PR
SPRLR17034-PSL-17-1-1-1	R	PR	PR
SPRLR75055-352-2-1	R, PR	PR	PR
BKNLR77003-PSL-9-1-1	R	—	—
IR36	R	R	R
RD7	R	M	M
RD11	R	PR	PR
RD23	R	R	R
C4-63 (green)	R	M	M

^aR = restorer (>80% spikelet fertility), PR = partial restorer (5- 80% spikelet fertility), M = maintainer (<5% spikelet fertility), — = damaged seedlings.

showing 5-80% as partial restorers. and those with less than 5% as maintainers.

RD23 and IR36 were effective restorers for all 3 CMS lines. RD11, SPRLR77034-PSL-17-1-1-1, and SPRLR75055-352-2-1 were effective

restorers only for V20A. SPRLR76037-2-164-1-1 was an effective maintainer for all CMS lines. RD7 and C4-63 (green) were effective restorers for V20A, but maintainers for IR46828A and IR46829A. □